

Subdirect Sum of Ternary Rings and Subdirectly Irreducible Ternary Rings

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Abstract.

In this paper we introduce the notions of subdirect sum of a family of ternary rings and the representation of a ternary ring as a subdirect sum of a family of ternary rings. We also introduce the notion of subdirectly irreducible ternary ring and characterize it. Lastly we characterize subdirectly irreducible Boolean ternary rings.

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1 Introduction

The introduction of mathematical literature of ternary algebraic system dated back to 1924. The notion of ternary algebraic system was first introduced by H. Prüfer [5] by the name 'schar'. After that W. Dörmte [2] further studied this type of algebraic system. In 1932, D.H. Lehmer [6] investigated certain ternary algebraic systems called triplexes which turn out to be a commutative ternary groups. Ternary groups are the special case of polyadic groups (in other terminologies which are known as n-groups) introduced by E. L. Post [4]. In 1971, W. G. Lister [7] introduced the notion of ternary ring and study some important properties of it. According to Lister [7], a ternary ring is an algebraic system consisting of a nonempty set R together with a binary operation, called addition and a ternary multiplication, which forms a commutative group relative to addition, a ternary semigroup relative to multiplication and left, right, lateral distributive laws hold.

The notion of subdirect sum of a family of rings has been introduced by N.H. McCoy [3]. He also introduced and characterized representation of a ternary ring as a subdirect sum of a family of rings. Following Birkhoff [1], he introduced the notion of subdirectly irreducible ring and characterize it. In this paper we introduce the notions of subdirect sum of a family of ternary rings and a representation of a ternary ring as a subdirect sum of family of ternary rings. We obtain that "A ternary ring R has a representation as a subdirect sum of a family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$ if and only if for each $i \in I$, there exists homomorphism $\phi_i : R \longrightarrow R_i$ such that if $r (\neq 0) \in R$, then $\phi_i(r) \neq 0$, for all least one i ". and "A ternary ring R has a representation as a subdirect sum of a family of ternary rings

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$\{R_i : i \in I\}$ if and only if for each $i \in I$, there exists in R a two sided ideal K_i such that R/K_i is isomorphic to R_i and moreover $\bigcap K_i = \{0\}$ ". We also introduce subdirectly irreducible ternary rings. We prove that "Every ternary ring R is isomorphic to subdirect sum of subdirectly irreducible ternary rings which are homomorphic images of R ". Lastly we characterize subdirectly irreducible Boolean ternary rings.

Some earlier work of the authors on ternary ring and multiplicative ternary hyperring may be found in [8] and [9].

2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 A nonempty set R together with a binary operation, called addition and a ternary multiplication denoted by juxtaposition, is said to be a ternary ring if R is an additive commutative group satisfying the following properties:

- (i) $(abc)de = a(bcd)e = ab(cde)$,
- (ii) $(a+b)cd = acd + bcd$,
- (iii) $a(b+c)d = abd + acd$,
- (iv) $ab(c+d) = abc + abd$ for all $a, b, c, d, e \in R$.

Definition 2.2 A nonempty subset S of a ternary ring R is called a ternary subring of R if $(S, +)$ is a subgroup of $(R, +)$ and if $s_1 s_2 s_3 \in S$ for all $s_1, s_2, s_3 \in S$.

Definition 2.3 A ternary ring R admits an identity provided that there exist elements

$\{(e_i, f_i) \in R \times R (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)\}$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^n e_i f_i x = \sum_{i=1}^n e_i x f_i = \sum_{i=1}^n x e_i f_i = x$ for all $x \in R$. In this case the ternary ring R is said to be a ternary ring with identity $\{(e_i, f_i) : i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$. In particular, if there exists an element $e \in R$ such that $eex = exe = xee = x$ for all $x \in R$ then e is called a unital element of the ternary ring R .

It is obvious that $xye = (exe)ye = ex(eye) = exy$ and $xye = x(eye)e = xe(yee) = xey$ for all $x, y \in R$. Hence the following result follows.

Proposition 2.4 If e is a unital element of a ternary ring R then $exy = xey = xye$, for all $x, y \in R$.

We now define left(right, lateral) ideal of a ternary ring.

Definition 2.5 An additive subgroup I of a ternary ring R is called a left(right, lateral) ideal of R if $r_1 r_2 i$ (respectively $i r_1 r_2, r_1 i r_2$) $\in I$ for all $r_1, r_2 \in R$ and $i \in I$. If I is a left, a right and a lateral ideal of R then I is called an ideal of R .

Definition 2.6 Let R and R' be two ternary rings and f be a mapping which maps R into R' .

Then the mapping $f : R \rightarrow R'$ is called a homomorphism of R into R' if the following conditions hold:

$$f(a+b) = f(a) + f(b).$$

$$f(abc) = f(a)f(b)f(c).$$

for all $a, b, c \in R$.

Definition 2.7 A ternary ring R is called commutative if $x_1 x_2 x_3 = x_{\sigma(1)} x_{\sigma(2)} x_{\sigma(3)}$, where σ is a permutation of $\{1, 2, 3\}$ for all $x_1, x_2, x_3 \in R$.

Definition 2.8 A non-trivial ternary ring R with a unital element e is said to be a division ternary ring if for every element $a (\neq 0) \in R$ there exists an element $b \in R$ such that $abx = x$ and $xba = x$ for all $x \in R$.

Definition 2.9 Let R be a commutative ternary ring with a unital element e . Then R is called a ternary field if for every element $a(\neq 0) \in R$ there exists an element $b \in R$ such that $abx = x$ for all $x \in R$.

Proposition 2.10 A ternary field does not contain divisors of zero.

Definition 2.11 An element x of a ternary ring R is called idempotent if $x^3 = x$.

Definition 2.12 A ternary ring R is called a simple ternary ring if $R^3 \neq (0)$ and if it contains no nonzero proper ideal i.e. $\{0\}$ and R are only ideals of R .

Theorem 2.13 A commutative ternary ring R with a unital element e is a ternary field if and only if (0) and R are the only ideals of R .

Proof. Let R be a ternary field. Let $e(\neq 0)$ be a unital element of R . Let $I(\neq 0)$ be any ideal of R and $a(\neq 0) \in I$. Since R is a ternary field, there exists an element $b \in R$ such that $abx = x$ for all $x \in R$. Now $a \in I \Rightarrow x = abx \in I$ for all $x \in R$. So $I = R$. Hence R contains only two ideals (0) and R . Conversely let the condition hold. Let $a(\neq 0)$ be an element of R . Consider the ideal (a) of R . Since $(a) \neq (0)$, it follows that $(a) = R$. So $e \in (a)$. Since R is commutative, $(a) = aRR$; Then $e = \sum_{i=1}^n ar_i s_i$ for some $r_i, s_i \in R, i = 1, 2, \dots$. Now $x = eex = (\sum_{i=1}^n ar_i s_i)ex = a(\sum_{i=1}^n r_i s_i e)x = abx$ where $b = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i s_i e$. Thus there exists an element $b \in R$ such that $abx = x \quad \forall x \in R$. So R is a ternary field.

Corollary 2.14 Let $T_3 = \{0, f, -f\}$ Then T_3 is a ternary field in which '+' and ternary multiplication is defined by

+	0	f	-f
0	0	f	-f
f	f	-f	0
-f	-f	0	f

	a	b	c	abc
	f	f	f	f
	$-f$	$-f$	$-f$	$-f$
	f	f	$-f$	$-f$
	f	$-f$	f	$-f$
	$-f$	f	$-f$	f
	$-f$	f	f	$-f$
	$-f$	$-f$	f	f
	f	$-f$	$-f$	f

and the product three elements with at least one zero is zero and f and $-f$ are unital elements of T_3 .

Definition 2.15 Let R be a ternary ring and I be an ideal of R . Define the sets $a+I = \{a+x : x \in I\}$ for each $a \in R$ and $R/I = \{a+I : a \in R\}$. Then R/I forms a ternary ring with addition and multiplication defined by

$$(a+I) + (b+I) = (a+b) + I \quad \text{and}$$

$$(a+I)(b+I)(c+I) = abc + I$$

for all $a, b, c \in R$. This ternary ring R/I is called the quotient ternary ring of R by I .

Definition 2.16 Let R be a ternary ring such that $R \neq \{0\}$. A proper ideal I of R is called maximal if I is not contained in any other proper ideal of R , i.e for any ideal J of R , $I \subseteq J \subseteq R$ implies that either $I = J$ or $J = R$.

Theorem 2.17 Let R be a commutative ternary ring with a unital element e . Then an ideal M of R is maximal if and only if R/M is a ternary field.

Proof. Let R be a ternary ring with a unital element e . Let M be a maximal ideal of R . Since R is commutative with unital element e , R/M is also commutative with unital element $e+M$. Let $a+M \in R/M$ be such that $a+M \neq 0+M$. Then $a \notin M$. Hence the ideal $M+aRR$ properly contains M . Since M is a maximal ideal, we have $M+aRR = R$. This implies that there exists $m \in M$ and $r_i, s_i \in R, i=1, 2, \dots$ such that $m + \sum_{i=1}^n ar_i s_i = e$. Then $e+M = \sum_{i=1}^n (a+M)(r_i+M)(s_i+M)$. Now $x+M = (e+M)(e+M)(x+M) = (\sum_{i=1}^n (a+M)(r_i+M)(s_i+M))(e+M)(x+M) = (a+M)(\sum_{i=1}^n (r_i+M)(s_i+M)(e+M))(x+M)$. Thus there exists an elements $b+M \in R/M$ such that $(x+M) = (a+M)(b+M)(x+M)$ where $b+M = \sum_{i=1}^n (r_i+M)(s_i+M)(e+M)$. So R/M is ternary field. Conversely, suppose that R/M is a ternary field. Since R/M is a ternary field, $R \neq M$. Let I be an ideal of R such that $M \subset I \subseteq R$. Then there exists $a \in I$ such that $a \notin M$. Then $a+M \neq 0+M$. Since R/M is a ternary field, there exists an elements $b+M \in R/M$ and such that

$(a+M)(b+M)(x+M) = x+M$ for all $x+M \in R/M$. So in particular $(a+M)(b+M)(e+M) = e+M$ which implies $e - abe \in M$. This implies $e \in I$. Hence $I = R$. Therefore M is maximal.

3 Subdirect Sum of Ternary Rings and Subdirectly Irreducible Ternary Rings

Definition 3.1 Let $\{R_i : i \in I\}$ be a family of ternary rings indexed by the set I . Let $R = \{f : I \rightarrow \cup R_i$ such that $f(i) \in R_i, \forall i \in I\}$. We define addition and multiplication on R by

$$(f+g)(i) = f(i) + g(i) \quad \text{and}$$

$$(fgh)(i) = f(i)g(i)h(i).$$

for all $i \in I$. Then R forms a ternary ring. This ternary ring R is called the complete direct sum of the family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$. Let $R' = \{f : I \rightarrow \cup R_i$ such that $f(i) = 0$ for all most all $i\}$. Then R' is a ternary subring of R . This subring is called the discrete direct sum of the family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$.

Remark 3.2 For a finite set of ternary rings the notions of complete direct sum and that of discrete direct sum coincide.

Definition 3.3 Let $\{R_i : i \in I\}$ be a family of ternary rings indexed by the set I and R be their direct sum. For each $i \in I$, we define a mapping θ_i from R into R_i by $\theta_i(f) = f(i)$. This mapping θ_i is called projection on R .

Proposition 3.4 For each $i \in I$, $\theta_i : R \rightarrow R_i$ is an epimorphism of ternary rings.

Proof. Let $f, g \in R$. Now $\theta_i(f+g) = (f+g)(i) = f(i) + g(i) = \theta_i(f) + \theta_i(g)$ and $\theta_i(fgh) = (fgh)(i) = f(i)g(i)h(i) = \theta_i(f)\theta_i(g)\theta_i(h)$. Thus θ_i is a ternary ring morphism. Let $t \in R_i$. We now define a mapping $f : I \rightarrow \cup R_i$ by

$$f(j) = \begin{cases} t & \text{if } j = i \\ 0 & \text{if } j \neq i \end{cases}$$

Then, $\theta_i(f) = t$. So θ_i is surjective. Thus θ_i is a ternary ring epimorphism.

Definition 3.5 Let $\{R_i : i \in I\}$ be a family of ternary rings and R be their complete direct sum. A ternary subring R' of R is called a subdirect sum of $\{R_i : i \in I\}$ if $\theta_i(R') = R_i, \forall i \in I$, where $\theta_i : R \rightarrow R_i$ is the projection map.

Remark 3.6 For a given family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$, there may be many subdirect sums for the family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$.

For example, the complete direct sum and the discrete direct sum are subdirect sum of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$.

Definition 3.7 If a ternary ring R isomorphic to a subdirect sum T of a family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$, then T is called a representation of R as a subdirect sum of the family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$.

In this case if α is the isomorphism of R onto T and θ_i is the projection map then $\phi_i = \theta_i \circ \alpha$ is a homomorphism from R onto R_i . This homomorphism ϕ_i is called the natural homomorphism of R onto R_i .

Theorem 3.8 A ternary ring R has a representation as a subdirect sum of a family of ternary rings

$\{R_i : i \in I\}$ if and only if for each $i \in I$, there exists homomorphism $\phi_i : R \xrightarrow{\text{onto}} R_i$ such that if $r(\neq 0) \in R$, then $\phi_i(r) \neq 0$, for at least one i .

Proof. Suppose that R has a representation T as a subdirect sum of the family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$. Then there exists an isomorphism α from R onto T . Let θ_i be the projection map. Let $\phi_i = \theta_i \circ \alpha$. Then ϕ_i is a homomorphism from R onto R_i for each $i \in I$. Let $r(\neq 0) \in R$. Then $\alpha(r) \neq 0$ [as α is an isomorphism]. Since $\alpha(r) \in T$, there exists at least one $i \in I$ such that $\alpha(r)(i) \neq 0$. i.e. $\theta_i(\alpha(r)) \neq 0$ i.e. $(\theta_i \circ \alpha)(r) \neq 0$ i.e. $\phi_i(r) \neq 0$ for at least one i . Conversely assume the condition stated in the theorem. For each $r \in R$, we define a mapping $f_r : I \rightarrow \cup_{i \in I} R_i$ by $f_r(i) = \phi_i(r)$. Then $f_r \in S$, the complete direct sum of $\{R_i : i \in I\}$. Let $T = \{f_r : r \in R\}$. Let $f_{r_1}, f_{r_2} \in T$, where $r_1, r_2 \in R$. Now $(f_{r_1} + f_{r_2})(i) = f_{r_1}(i) + f_{r_2}(i) = \phi_i(r_1) + \phi_i(r_2) = \phi_i(r_1 + r_2)$ [as ϕ_i is a homomorphism] $= f_{r_1+r_2}(i)$ for all $i \in I$. Thus $f_{r_1} + f_{r_2} = f_{r_1+r_2} \in T$.

Let $r_1, r_2, r_3 \in R$. $(f_{r_1} f_{r_2} f_{r_3})(i) = f_{r_1}(i) f_{r_2}(i) f_{r_3}(i) = \phi_i(r_1) \phi_i(r_2) \phi_i(r_3) = \phi_i(r_1 r_2 r_3)$ [as ϕ is a homomorphism] $= f_{r_1 r_2 r_3}(i)$, $\forall i \in I$. Therefore $f_{r_1} f_{r_2} f_{r_3} = f_{r_1 r_2 r_3} \in T$. Again $(-f_{r_1})(i) = -f_{r_1}(i) = -\phi_i(r_1) = \phi_i(-r_1)$ [as ϕ is a homomorphism] $= f_{-r_1}(i)$, $\forall i \in I$. Therefore $-f_{r_1} = f_{-r_1} \in T$. Thus T is a ternary subring of S . Let $f_r \in T$. Now $\theta_i(f_r) = f_r(i) = \phi_i(r) \in R_i$ for $f_r \in T$. So, $\theta_i(T) \subseteq R_i$. Let $r_i \in R_i$. Since ϕ_i is onto, there exists $r \in R$ such that $\phi_i(r) = r_i$. i.e. $f_r(i) = r_i$ i.e. $\theta_i(f_r) = r_i$. Thus $r_i = \theta_i(f_r) \in \theta_i(T)$. So $R_i \subseteq \theta_i(T)$. Therefore $R_i = \theta_i(T)$. Thus T is the subdirect sum of the family of ternary subrings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$. We now define a mapping $\alpha : R \rightarrow T$ by $\alpha(r) = f_r$. Let $r_1, r_2, r_3 \in R$. Then $\alpha(r_1 + r_2) = f_{r_1+r_2} = f_{r_1} + f_{r_2} = \alpha(r_1) + \alpha(r_2)$ and $\alpha(r_1 r_2 r_3) = f_{r_1 r_2 r_3} = f_{r_1} f_{r_2} f_{r_3} = \alpha(r_1) \alpha(r_2) \alpha(r_3)$. Therefore α is a ternary ring morphism. Let $r \in \text{Ker } \alpha$. Therefore $\alpha(r) = 0 \Rightarrow (\alpha(r))(i) = 0$, $\forall i \in I \Rightarrow f_r(i) = 0 \Rightarrow \phi_i(r) = 0$, $\forall i \in I \Rightarrow r = 0$ (by the given condition). Therefore α is injective. Obviously α is surjective. Hence α is an isomorphism. Thus R has a representation T as a subdirect sum of the family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$.

Remark 3.9 Since $(\theta_i \circ f)(r) = \theta_i(f(r)) = \theta_i(f_r) = f_r(i) = \phi_i(r)$, $\forall r \in R$, $\theta_i \circ f = \phi_i$. Thus the homomorphism ϕ_i in the above theorem is nothing but the natural homomorphism.

Theorem 3.10 A ternary ring R has a representation as a subdirect sum of a family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$ if and only if for each $i \in I$, there exists in R a two sided ideal K_i such that R/K_i is isomorphic to R_i and moreover $\cap K_i = (0)$.

Proof. Suppose that R has a representation as a subdirect sum of a family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$. Then for each $i \in I$ there exists a homomorphism $\phi_i : R \xrightarrow{\text{onto}} R_i$ such that if $r(\neq 0) \in R$ then $\phi_i(r) \neq 0$, for at least one i . Let $K_i = \text{Ker } \phi_i$, $i \in I$. Then for each $i \in I$, K_i is a two sided ideal of R . Again by the "First Isomorphism Theorem" on ternary ring $R/\text{Ker } \phi_i \cong R_i$, $\forall i \in I$ i.e. $R/K_i \cong R_i$, $\forall i \in I$. Let $r \in \cap K_i \Rightarrow r \in K_i = \text{Ker } \phi_i$, $\forall i \in I \Rightarrow \phi_i(r) = 0$, $\forall i \in I \Rightarrow r = 0$. Thus $\cap K_i = (0)$. Conversely suppose that for each $i \in I$, there exists a two sided ideal K_i in R such that $R/K_i \cong R_i$ and $\cap K_i = (0)$. Let $\pi_i : R \rightarrow R/K_i$ be natural epimorphism for each $i \in I$ and $\alpha_i : R/K_i \rightarrow R_i$ be the isomorphism, $\forall i \in I$. Let $\phi_i = \alpha_i \circ \pi_i$. Then for each $i \in I$ there exists a homomorphism ϕ_i from R onto R_i . Now suppose that $r(\neq 0) \in R$. Then $r \notin (0) = \bigcap_{i \in I} K_i \Rightarrow r \notin K_i = \text{Ker } \pi_i$, for at least one i . $\Rightarrow \pi_i(r) \neq 0 \Rightarrow (\alpha_i \circ \pi_i)(r) \neq 0 \Rightarrow \phi_i(r) \neq 0$, for at least one i (since α_i is an isomorphism). Then R has a representation as a subdirect sum of a family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$.

Definition 3.11 A ternary ring R is said to be subdirectly irreducible if for every representation T of R as a subdirect sum of a family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$, there exists an $i \in I$ such that the homomorphism ϕ_i from R onto R_i is an isomorphism where $\phi_i = \theta_i \circ \alpha$, θ_i is the projection map and α is the isomorphism from R onto T .

Trivial ternary rings i.e the ternary rings consisting of zero element only are assumed to be subdirectly irreducible.

Theorem 3.12 A nonzero ternary ring R is subdirectly irreducible if and only if the intersection of all nonzero ideals of R is a nonzero ideal.

Proof. Suppose that the nonzero ternary ring R is subdirectly irreducible. Let $\{K_i : i \in I\}$ be the family of all nonzero ideals of R . If possible, let $\bigcap_{i \in I} K_i = (0)$. Let $R_i = R/K_i$. Then $\{R_i : i \in I\}$ is a family of ternary rings. Now for each $i \in I$, there exists a homomorphism ϕ_i from R onto R_i (natural epimorphism). Now suppose that $r(\neq 0) \in R$. Then $r \notin (0) = \bigcap_{i \in I} K_i \Rightarrow r \notin K_i \Rightarrow \phi_i(r) \neq 0$ for at least one $i \in I$. So R has a representation T as subdirect sum of family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$. Since for any $i \in I$, $\phi_i : R \rightarrow R_i$ is not an isomorphism, it follows that R is not subdirectly irreducible, a contradiction. So intersection of all nonzero ideals of R is a nonzero ideal. Conversely suppose that intersection of all nonzero ideals of R is a nonzero ideal. Let T be a representation of R as a subdirect sum of a family of ternary rings $\{R_i : i \in I\}$. Then for each $i \in I$ there exists an onto homomorphism $\phi_i : R \rightarrow R_i$ such that for $r(\neq 0) \in R$, $\phi_i(r) \neq 0$ for at least one i . Let K be the intersection of all nonzero ideals of R , then $K \neq (0)$. Let $r(\neq 0) \in K$. So there exists an onto homomorphism $\phi_i : R \rightarrow R_i$ such that $\phi_i(r) \neq 0$. So $r \notin \text{Ker } \phi_i$. But K is the smallest nonzero ideal of R . So, this is possible only when $\text{Ker } \phi_i = (0)$, which implies that ϕ_i is a monomorphism. Also ϕ_i is an epimorphism. Thus ϕ_i is an isomorphism. Thus there exists an $i \in I$ such that ϕ_i from R onto R_i is an isomorphism. So R is subdirectly irreducible.

Corollary 3.13 (1) Every division ternary ring or ternary field is subdirectly irreducible.

Proof. Let R be a division ternary ring or a field. Then $\{0\}$ and R are only ideals. Here R is the only nonzero ideal. Hence the result.

Corollary 3.14 Every simple ternary ring is subdirectly irreducible.

Theorem 3.15 Every ternary ring R is isomorphic to a subdirect sum of subdirectly irreducible ternary rings which are homomorphic images of R .

Proof. Obviously we may restrict ourselves to the case in which R has nonzero elements. Let $a(\neq 0) \in R$. Let $\mathcal{F} = \{I : I \text{ is an ideal of } R \text{ such that } a \notin I\}$. Since $(0) \in \mathcal{F}$, $\mathcal{F} \neq \emptyset$. Now applying Zorn's lemma, we can find a maximal element M_a in \mathcal{F} . Then M_a is an ideal of R , maximal with respect to the property that $a \notin M_a$. i.e if N is an ideal of R such that $M_a \subsetneq N$ then $a \in N$. Let $R_a = R/M_a$. Then $\{R_a : a(\neq 0) \in R\}$ is a family of ternary rings. Let N/M_a be a nonzero ideal of R/M_a . Then $M_a \subsetneq N$. This implies that $a \in N$. Now $a + M_a \neq 0 + M_a$ and $a + M_a \in N/M_a$. This is true for all nonzero ideals N/M_a of R/M_a . Thus the intersection of all nonzero ideals of R/M_a is nonzero. Consequently $R_a = R/M_a$ is subdirectly irreducible. Now we consider the family of subdirectly irreducible ternary rings $\{R_a : a(\neq 0) \in R\}$ where $R_a = R/M_a$. Now for each $a \in R \setminus \{0\}$, there exists an ideal M_a in R such that $R/M_a \cong R_a$ [actually $R/M_a = R_a$]. If possible let $b(\neq 0) \in \bigcap_{a \in R \setminus \{0\}} M_a$. Then $b \in M_b$, a contradiction. So $\bigcap_{a \in R \setminus \{0\}} M_a = (0)$. Consequently R has a representation T as subdirect sum of the family of subdirectly irreducible ternary rings $\{R_a : a \in R \setminus \{0\}\}$. Thus R is

isomorphic to the subdirect sum of the family of subdirectly irreducible ternary rings $\{R_a : a \in R \setminus \{0\}\}$, which are homomorphic images of R .

Theorem 3.16 *A subdirectly irreducible commutative ternary ring with a unital element f and with more than one element and with no nonzero nilpotent elements is a ternary field.*

Proof. Let R be a subdirectly irreducible commutative ternary ring with a unital element f and with more than one element and with no nonzero nilpotent element. Let e be an idempotent element of R . Consider the ideals eRR and $A = \{r - eer : r \in R\}$. Now let $x \in eRR \cap A$. Then $x = \sum_{i=1}^n e r_i s_i = r - eer$, where $r_i, s_i, r \in R, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Now $eex = x$ [as e is an idempotent element]. Again $eex = eer - eeer = eer - eer = 0$. So $eRR \cap A = (0)$. Since R is subdirectly irreducible either $eRR = (0)$ or $A = (0)$. If $eRR = (0)$, then $e = eee \in eRR = (0)$; so $e = 0$. If $A = (0)$ then $r = eer$ for all $r \in R$. So e is a unital element of R . Let $z (\neq 0) \in$ intersection of all non-zero ideals of R . Consider the ideal z^2R . Then $z^2R \neq (0)$, for R contains no non-zero nilpotent elements. Now $z \in z^2R$. So $z = z^2t$ for some $t \in R$. Then $ztf = z^2tff = ztzf$ [as R is commutative] $= zt.z^2tff = z^3t^3f^3$ [as R is commutative] $= (ztf)^3$. So, ztf is an idempotent of R . So $ztf = 0$ or ztf is a unital element of R . If $ztf = 0$, then $z = z^2tff = z(ztf)f = 0$, which is a contradiction. So ztf is a unital element of R . Let $I (\neq (0))$ be an ideal of R . Then $z \in I \Rightarrow ztf \in I \Rightarrow x = x(ztf)(ztf) \in I, \forall x \in R$. So $I = R$. Thus R is a commutative ternary ring with a unital element and (0) and R are the only ideals of R . So R is a ternary field.

4 Subdirectly Irreducible Boolean Ternary Rings

Definition 4.1 *A ternary ring in which every element is idempotent is called a Boolean ternary ring.*

Theorem 4.2 *A commutative Boolean ternary ring R is subdirectly irreducible if and only if $R \cong T_3$ [defined in corollary 2.14]*

Proof. Suppose that the commutative Boolean ternary ring R is subdirectly irreducible. Let $e \in R$. Now consider the ideals eRR and $A = \{r - err : r \in R\}$ of R . Let $x \in eRR \cap A$. Then $x = \sum_{i=1}^n e r_i s_i = r - eer$, where $r_i, s_i, r \in R, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Now, $eex = x$ [as e is an idempotent element]. Again, $eex = eer - eeer = eer - eer = 0 = x$. So $x = eex = 0$. Thus $eRR \cap A = (0)$. Since R is subdirectly irreducible $eRR = (0)$ or $A = (0)$. If $eRR = (0)$ then $e = e^3 \in eRR = (0)$ i.e $e = 0$. If $A = (0)$ then $r = eer$ for all $r \in R$. So e is a unital element of R . Thus every non zero element of R is a unital element of R . Let $e (\neq 0), f (\neq 0) \in R$. Then $e + f \in R$. So $e + f = 0$ or $e + f$ is a unital element of R . If $e + f = 0$ then $e = -f$. Let $e + f \neq 0$. Then $e + f$ is a unital element of R . So $(e + f)(e + f)e = e$. This implies that $e^3 + efe + fee + ffe = e$ i.e $e + f + f + e = e$ or $2f = -e$. Similarly we get $2e = -f$. Thus $2e - e = 2f - f$ i.e $e = f$. Thus $R \cong T_3$. Conversely suppose that $R \cong T_3$. Since T_3 is a ternary field, so T_3 and hence R is subdirectly irreducible.

Theorem 4.3 *A ternary ring R is isomorphic to a subdirect sum of ternary fields $\{R_i : i \in I\}$ where $R_i \cong T_3 \forall i \in I$ if and only if R is a commutative Boolean ternary ring.*

Proof. Let R be a commutative Boolean ternary ring. Then R is isomorphic to a subdirect sum of subdirectly irreducible ternary ring $\{R_i : i \in I\}$ which are homomorphic images of R . Since R is commutative Boolean, each homomorphic image R_i of R is also commutative Boolean. Also, each R_i is subdirectly irreducible. So, each $R_i \cong T_3$. Then each R_i is a ternary field. Thus the commutative Boolean ternary ring R is isomorphic to a subdirect sum of ternary fields $\{R_i : i \in I\}$, where $R_i \cong T_3$,

$\forall i \in I$. Conversely suppose that R is isomorphic to subdirect sum, say T of ternary fields $\{R_i : i \in I\}$, where $R_i \cong T_3$, for each $i \in I$. Let $f \in T$ then $f(i) \in R_i$, for $i \in I$. Since $R_i \cong T_3$. $(f(i))^3 = f(i)$ i.e $f(i).f(i).f(i) = f(i)$ i.e $f^3(i) = f(i)$, for all $i \in I$. So $f^3 = f$. Thus each element of T is idempotent. Again $f(i) \in R_i \cong T_3$. Hence, each element of R is also idempotent(as RT). Again since each $R_i \cong T_3$, each R_i is commutative. So the complete direct sum and hence the subdirect sum T of ternary fields $\{R_i : i \in I\}$ is commutative. Thus R is commutative. So R is a commutative Boolean ternary ring.

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